

Empathy @ Design Research:

A phenomenological study on young designers experiencing participatory design

Jin Ma* Denny Kwok-leung Ho** C.K. Peter Chuah***

* *School of Design, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University
Hong Kong, China, ma.jin@polyu.edu.hk*

** *Department of Applied Social Sciences, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University
Hong Kong, China, ssdenny@polyu.edu.hk*

*** *School of Design, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University
Hong Kong, China, sd.ckpeterchuah@polyu.edu.hk*

Abstract: This paper presents a method of understanding the users involved in design research which advocates participatory design and inclusive design. This method is an attempt to fill the gap that has been left in design literature about feasible ways of understanding users, in response to the suggestion that users' involvement in design process is important. We start with illustrating designers' attitudes associated with the suppression of users' experience and designers' self experience within the designer-as-the-expert framework in the existing design practices; then we move on to show how empathy is employed as a design research process in this respect. The importance of personal description, the formation of intersubjectivity and the three layers of embodied empathy are highlighted. We adopt the phenomenological perspective to analyze the layers of embodied relationship between users and novice designers and the extent to which they are interrupted by designers' natural attitudes so as to shed some light on feasible ways of mutual understanding between designers and users. The analysis is based on the research notes of the Design.Live Workshop (Hong Kong 2009).

Key words: *participatory design, inclusive design, empathy, phenomenology, active-design-partners.*

1. Introduction

Design research, as a collective term that covers a wide range of research activities directed to different subject matters and purposes, has been largely affected by the rationalist epistemology [1] for a long time. Accordingly, the dominant concern focuses on the exploration of the elements of design activities including the object, the actor, the context, and the process, whereas the creator role has been assigned solely to the designer [2]. Users, being part of the context, remain as *passive* information providers in this paradigm. The emergence of participatory design movement in the early 1970s is an attempt to redefine 'users' as *co-creators*, and to address the issues of developing creative cooperation [3]. Nevertheless, the forms, the extent and the nature of cooperation have not been clearly spelt out.

In our review of the recent literature on participatory design and co-design, we have identified three themes in relation to 'how we design', namely, the *roles* of participants, the *space*, and the *experience and process*. They

are particularly of our interest because they are relevant to the prevailing focus of the current participatory design research and practices, as many researchers advocate [4]. In the subsequent parts of this paper, we will sketch a rough picture of the existing participatory design practices in line with these three themes. Then we will draw findings from our experiences in an inclusive design workshop to address these interrelated issues. By virtue of reflections on these experiences, we attempt to elucidate some aspects in participatory design that have been overlooked, and we argue for the importance of designers attending to them to advance the understanding of co-creation and mutual knowledge development. Hopefully, our efforts can shed light on the concerns regarding who benefits from such design practices. This discussion is informed by the insights of phenomenological approach to the concept of empathy in social research and the experiences of our involvement in an inclusive design workshop advocated by Cassim [5] and Lee [6].

2. A brief critique of participatory design

The big family of participatory design or co-design advocates open-ended inquiries in design practices through the inclusion of people who may eventually be influenced by such practices. This advocacy is rooted in a criticism that the conventional designer-centered practices exclude multiple voices. However, contemporary participatory design practices, which have a history of over forty years, exhibit diverse and multidirectional interest concerning the issues as to ‘how we design’, ‘what we design’, and ‘who designs’. Such diversity stems from various historical origins [7]. Participatory design within the Scandinavian heritage emerged in the 1970s, driven by a genuine curiosity towards people’s creativity that calls for collaborative idea generation [7]. Another participatory trend emerged in the UK, and was formally termed as “Design Participation” at the Design Research Society’s Conference in 1971. It stresses design for social needs and a transition from craft orientation towards more openly transparent processes and methods [7]. A third trend named as Co-creation, according to Sanders & Stappers [3], has evolved from user-centered design approach that has been prevailing in the USA, and has consolidated a shift towards redefinition of the roles of the designer, the researcher and the ‘user’.

Clearly, participatory design practices have originated from different traditions, grow and develop into many overlapping concerns embedded in the fabric of design, in all forms and processes, as long as participation occurs. We have identified three issues out of these traditions to illustrate the significance of our inputs into the participatory design processes.

2.1. The roles of different participants

Almost every approach to participatory design emphasizes the need to rethink the roles of the participants, especially those who are known as ‘users’. ‘Users’ are carefully termed as participants [8], or co-creators [6], to indicate such a need. The advocates of co-creation criticize that ‘users’ are not necessary to actively take part in design within the conventional understanding of designer-user relationship, because, just like in the user-centered design framework, ‘users’ are viewed as rather passive providers, while designers (and researchers) are active leaders. By seeing ‘users’ as active-design-partners in inclusive design practices [4, 6], designers’ roles are also reshaped as “developers, facilitators, and generators” [4]. More specific efforts are made, e.g., Sanders and Stappers [3] summarize the roles of each participatory party in this way: (i) the users as “experts in their experiences”, co-creators, or both consumers and designers [9]; (ii) the researchers from translators to facilitators who make the whole plan, conceive the methods, and facilitate the process; (iii) the designers as providers of

design skills and expert knowledge. Taking these three versions of role-assigning theorizing in design practices, we could identify the basic components of each categorization about the roles of designers and user-participants. In our view, regarding users as experts, it is to see the authority of users as grounded on knowledge. Here arises the question as to the nature of knowledge, which could be professional knowledge, scientific knowledge, tacit knowledge or the knowledge that makes laymen's daily life accomplishment possible. Given that users are the experts based on those kinds of knowledge other than professional and scientific, there is a necessity for the division of labor among users, designers and researchers through which users' role is viewed to be supported by laymen's knowledge, designers by 'designerly' ways of professional knowing and researchers by scientific knowledge. It seems that the concept of co-creation then arrives at a clear understanding. It is a web of relationships composed of three different roles. However, in face of integrating the three roles into a unified practice, there arises the issue of power. In turn, we encounter the further political issues about authority, leadership and decision-making. It leads to the question of when professional knowledge rules, or when laymen's knowledge matters. Furthermore, most versions of role-(re)defining are rather fixed with corresponding anticipations put on each role, which are yet to be fabricated into situated and evolving design processes. If this is the case, it seems that we only pay lip-service to the concept of co-creation, without making any clear sense of the genuine nature of co-creation.

We however are inclined to leave such a role-defining task behind, as it is leading not only to the situation in which design is overwhelmed by administrative issues, but also to ignorance of the nature of daily social practice. In our view, in any design process, no professional person could purify oneself by discarding one's tacit knowledge, scientific knowledge and knowledge used in daily natural setting. There is no way for a professional to strip him/herself of their personal perspective. In order to avoid suppressing other's participation in design, we are not going to re-configure and re-assign the roles to different duties in design; instead we suggest the use of empathy as the methodological and conceptual tool to achieve co-creation.

2.2. Space in participatory design

Another aspect that has been neglected in the participatory design is the study of spatial dimension which importantly allows us to understand human beings' experiences, since being in the world means an inescapable position that is situated in space that inevitably intertwines with other factors such as time. The spatial dimension associated with the working environments, arrangements of design process as well as methods and tools should be further developed. In Brodersen, Dindler and Iversen's approach to participatory design by staging imaginative places to arrive at creative transcendence, they touch upon the underdeveloped factor of place and space in participatory design practices. They understand "places" as "the 'orders' and stability by which we relate to the world [10]," but they did not elaborate further on the long and rich discussions within philosophy and humanist geography, e.g., de Certeau's work [11]. We take the phenomenological perspective as the tool to open up the possibility of relating space and participatory design experience.

2.3. Experiences and Processes of participatory design

In many participatory design or co-design processes, designers and researchers attempt to oversee design processes from a rather distanced perspective [12]. While designer's self experience is largely overlooked, user

experience is addressed as an independent objective entity that can be “discovered”. Experiences dissolve into the descriptions about procedures, methods and tools, and outcomes, so they themselves are insufficiently explored. User experience is thus disconnected from how designers experience such co-creations.

Phenomenology, however, emphasizes the relationship between what is experienced and how it is experienced, which blurs the dichotomy of subject and object. In other words, there is no such thing as an independent ‘I’ being a subject. Instead, ‘I’ see the world through the relationship between the world and ‘I’. ‘I’ can only understand the world that the ‘I’ intend toward, and by seeing the world, ‘I’ see myself in turn. This intertwining relationship is the foundation for us to understand the ‘other’. And only in this way can reflection and empathy, as a means to approach experiences, be grounded. Nonetheless, such a relationship is missing in the existing participatory design discussion. Some researchers, e.g., Mattelmäki [13], are inspired by the potential impacts of reflection and empathy on design process, but have not elaborated on the implications of seeing them as critical concepts of a rigorous methodology for design. By introducing experience disclosed in reflection and empathy, participatory design may develop toward an ongoing reflective process that could better include multiple voices, from which all participants may thus benefit.

3. Empathy matters

Users’ needs and experience have been introduced to design practices by user-centered design and participatory design, which also challenge the traditional experts-vs.-users power structure. Polarized between user exclusion and user inclusion, the whole spectrum of design practices is shaped by designers’ understanding of users. What follows is the question of ‘how’ to understand the user.

We would like to address this question in the light of the conception of empathy. Empathy is the English translation of the German term *Einfühlung*, which means “feeling into, or gently sensing another person or an object in the process of trying to appreciate it [14].” This term has been generally understood as “entering another’s world” when applied to the human world. Phenomenological philosopher Stein, who follows Husserl’s work *Ideas I*, took up the broad discussion on what happens at the moment of empathy by further explicating it as: “(1) the emergence of the experience, (2) the fulfilling explication, and (3) the comprehensive objectification of the explained experience” [15]. Husserl [16] developed the concept of empathy by seeing it as constitutive of the other and as the condition of possible knowledge of an existing outer world. Finlay summarizes that “empathy can be understood as feeling with the Other – a reciprocal process where one seeks to find ways to allow the Other to present him- or himself to and through one [14].” Finlay [14] further suggests that, there are three interrelated layers of an intersubjective process to achieve empathy: *connecting-of*, *acting-into*, and *merging-with*. Hence we see opportunities of practicing empathy in participatory design as it provides the conditions for advancing individual’s knowledge and experience through a reciprocal reflection situated in the relationship between a person and the ‘other’. We view it as a rigorous approach toward better understanding of the user and true inclusion.

Based on our observations of the Design.Live Workshop 2009¹, we found that understanding users, however, has much to do with the attitudes of the designers in their interaction with the users. As Lee [4] points out, the new modality of relationship between designers and users advocated by participatory design has been more about attitude change and less about practical information for how to conduct design participation. In our analysis, we found that the problematic natural attitudes, associated with designers' roles and self experience, must be noted. By natural attitude, we mean the default perspective that we start off from, the one in which we intend the world originally, and the taken-for-grantedness in which we are immersed when experiencing other people, objects and things. The change of attitude thus cannot be achieved within natural attitudes simply by changing from seeing designers themselves as experts to placing the designers and the users on the same plane. We found that if designers are unaware of their natural attitudes and thereby unable to suspend and reflect on them, the user experience they aim at understanding will be "contaminated" and less relevant to users themselves. To understand the user, we need to explicate the natural attitudes entangled with the three-layered process of empathy.

In line with the aforementioned three themes of participatory design, we first draw our experiences in the workshop to illustrate how natural attitudes impede the three-layered process of empathy to different extents in 3.1 and 3.2; and then in 3.3 we use a case from the same workshop to propose how empathy could be achieved.

3.1. Roles of participants and identity in presentation of experience

To elicit the interrelated natural attitudes associated with designers' changing role, we first draw insights from the phenomenological approach to the structure of identity in manifolds. Sokolowski [17] maintains that the identity of an object is revealed through continuously experiencing the manifolds of presentation of the object. The identity cannot be 'assigned' separately from the way it is experienced. If a *role* is the way how a participant functions in design activities, it is actually a manifold of presentation of that participant, where one's identity emerges. Within a consistent and unreflected relationship such as experts-vs.-users, each party's role and identity match well. Designers are accustomed to roles as creators, helpers, and experts when design is generally understood as a problem solving process. The identity of 'problem solvers' emerges when designers carrying out design process that routinely begins with problem identification. Correspondingly, within such a process, users' identity as 'problem-carriers' is established and reinforced through the ways they function merely as the 'end users', which eventually becomes their designated role. Only when a mismatch occurs is the original relationship challenged by an alternative attitude. E.g., if the intended role of the users as co-creators is never practiced as

¹ The Design.Live Workshop in Hong Kong 2009 was developed into a teenager version based on the 48 Hour Inclusive Design Challenge template in Hong Kong 2008 [6]. It aims at helping potential and novice design students experience the inclusive design process to glimpse the nature of design in the shifting social context, particularly in the fuzzy front end that increasingly includes the participation of (potential) users. The participants included a group of students from both the secondary schools in Hong Kong and year one design students from Shangtou University, China; a group of creative partners comprising disabled and elderly people from Hong Kong; and a group of volunteers with either design or social sciences background from a local university in Hong Kong serving the role of facilitator. As a further localized version, the workshop adopted Cantonese to enhance the communication for both educational and executive purposes. Eight design teams in total were set up, each consisting of one disabled/elderly active-design-partner and approximately 10-15 student designers, and a facilitator. It started with a half day of presentations about design in general and inclusive design given by the local designers in Hong Kong and workshop organizers, in order to prepare the high school students and college freshmen with necessary knowledge about what they were expected to do. Students were divided into groups ahead of being introduced to their design partners and facilitators.

such, the new identity would not have the chance to emerge. The formation of the new co-creation relationship only happens when alternative identities can be perceived and earned through supporting roles in experiences.

Focusing on how to understand user experience, we conducted phenomenological analysis of the reflections generated based on the authors' observation notes about the Design.Live Workshop. We discovered that the willingness of the student designers to listen to the voices and the demands of active-design-partners (disabled and elderly people) was associated with the students' interpretations of designers' role. We identified a type of designers' interpretation of their social role on the basis of our observations of two young male students who already have specific ideas of design. They conceived design as having a clear procedure, well-defined clients' needs and product orientation. This type of student designer, directed by those ideas, would promptly execute their methods of needs identification and the construction of the design brief. As a result, their dominance within the group would leave other participants self-restricted and passive. In this case, these two young male students admitted that they had previous design experiences and knew clearly what design was. One was very proud that he had won a number of awards. As shown in the process of their interaction with the active-design-partner, it was very difficult for them to change their mindsets. Thus, under their dominance, the final design products are those mainly for the purpose of 'assisting' or even 'helping' the active-design-partner who throughout the workshop was excluded from dialogues and decision-making process. As reported by the facilitator in this group, the active-design-partner asked in the workshop the next morning whether the group members were willing to listen to his personal stories and desires at all. Clearly the active-design-partner was fed up with the dominance of the 'active' expert-like 'designers' and let down by the silence of the rest. The intended users' identity as active co-creators in this workshop did not emerge in the context of expert dominance and the expected users' role. There was few connections between the 'designers' and the active-design-partners due to the formers' distanced attitude. The situation got worse when the rest of the students just sat there baffled with the 'correct' ways of digging out the data which could represent the 'needs' of the active-design-partner. In the face of a concrete person with flesh and blood, 'designers' remained obsessed with sorting out the major characteristics of the 'imagined' user. This is related to another natural attitude that further disconnects user's identity from experience.

Suppose we are thinking of the concept of users, and in reality, we see a user in front of us. It is a very easy way of conceiving the 'real' user in front of us as the representative of the collective group: *the User*. It seems that through design research we reconstitute the concept of 'the user' with a general identity, which is irrelevant to the experience of the particular user involved in design. Sokolowski [17] has pointed out the problem in such a conception. He uses the concepts of parts and wholes, where "wholes can be analyzed into two different kinds of parts: pieces and moments. *Pieces* are parts that can subsist and be presented even apart from the whole; they can be detached from their wholes. Pieces can also be called independent parts....*Moments* are parts that cannot subsist or be presented apart from the whole to which they belong; they cannot be detached. Moments are nonindependent parts (italics in original)." The identity of a user is a moment; it bears an essential relation to that person, who is a living being with experience, rather than a sum of empty conceptual categories. But the identity is often caricatured by being turned into a piece, into an independent conceptual construction that could exist and be presented and understood apart from the experience that discloses it. Verbeek and Kockelkoren also pointed

out that “designers define users in terms of their taste, competence, motives, aspirations, and political prejudices [18].” We talk about the concept of ‘the user’ consisting of a collective identity, rather than experience, and depict the identity with an abstract persona. However, in phenomenological analysis, a user’s desire and stories should be seen as moments of the user in question, which are inseparable aspects of the specific user. Conceptualizing empty identities by taking the moments as pieces is another natural attitude in design, resulting from design’s Platonic tradition by abstracting concepts from the whole of human experience, and considering experiences to be “only the derivative ‘copies’ of primordial ideas [18].” Both attitudes, abstract conceptualization and problem solving, are intertwined and further lead to suppression of user experience from expression.

These two mixed natural attitudes do not provide conditions that allow users to reveal their experience, and the ‘connecting of’ stage tends to be interrupted. This is revealed in another case from this workshop, the one with 84-year old Granny T as an active-design-partner. When Granny T began to tell her personal stories huddled by the students, she seemed happy and excited. However, the situation changed after the facilitator encouraged the student designers to identify more problems that Granny T might encounter in everyday life and to construct a persona. Subsequently, the students began to take the lead by asking various questions while Granny T’s answers gradually became ‘simpler and shorter’. But the students told the facilitator that they were frustrated because most of the time Granny T did not give them ‘direct’ or ‘valuable’ answers. “She’s not a true user! She doesn’t have any problems at all!” a student designer exclaimed. Feeling disappointed by ‘fruitless’ problem identification, the students began to ask desperate questions such as: “What is most inconvenient in your everyday life?”; “Do you have any regrets about things that you haven’t done yet?” But Granny T’s response was brief, “everything is just fine.” Understanding user experience was clearly informed by pragmatic problem-solving thinking. The shortly enjoyed old-and-young relationship was terminated by an experts-vs.-users relationship. The moment the students became impatient with Granny T’s story-telling and thought it was heading in a wrong direction, they lost a design opportunity which otherwise might be of interest to both granny as a partner and students as designers.

While Granny T’s identity was perceived as ordinary, as shown in the students’ accounts “she’s an ordinary old lady in perfect health because she walks very fast and refused any help in public transportation”, the student designers tried hard to construct a conceptual persona based on the anticipated problems that they could find. Granny T was dehumanized as an objectified information provider among many others, and abstracted to a concept of ‘the user’ which carries the collective identity with a high degree of representativeness. In the face of the 84-year-old, the 18-year-old youngsters found it extremely difficult to understand what being old means. The only focus is on the pieces that constitute the whole in the process of thinking about and understanding individual users – moments of the whole had been totally neglected. So they did not ask Granny T about her illness although they knew she had a medical appointment in that afternoon; they did not notice Granny T’s experiences in transportation when they accompanied her back to the nursing home where she lives; there seemed to be a lack of interest in knowing her ways of arranging her room, her living with her illness, and her personal history of being an acrobat in Temple Street during her early days. Connecting to the ‘other’ is the first layer of empathy. Carrying with these natural attitudes, however, designers tend to approach users with an

objectified stance that, as a result, widens the distance. There were few signs of connections in between.

3.2. Space is the moment of personal experience

In the process toward the intersubjectively appreciated experience, not only user experience tends to be immediately suppressed by the attitudes analyzed above, but also designers' self experience is largely neglected. Here we attempt to discuss space's impacts on our bodily experience to illustrate how 'acting into' the other's experience by understanding self experience can be affected by this layer of natural attitude. Merleau-Ponty [19] said, "[T]he body is the vehicle of being in the world." And more than this, the body is the vehicle for understanding the world. We argue that a designer equipped with knowledge which neglects bodily experience is less capable of truly understanding user's needs. Neither the practices in which designers act as professionals nor those in which researchers as social activists have investigated designers' bodily experience, which, in our views, may function as a vehicle and context to disclose user experience. Here is where empathy comes in. Bodily experience is context-dependent, so it is somewhat crucial to understand user experience in a concrete situation. Further probing into the second case in the workshop, we found how the meanings of situation could change the views of the designers in the process of design research. Take the experience of the journey to the nursing home as an example, we reflected on the ways the student designers interacted with Granny T to open up opportunities to understand user experience that had been suppressed.

In the afternoon session when Granny T told the participants she needed to go back to her nursing home, they asked if she was happy to have them accompany her back and visit the nursing home. She agreed. Along that journey, we discovered how the meaning of space affected designers' experiences which in turn bore on the results of their actions. During the intensive workshop, before the journey, the participants were situated in a classroom-like environment equipped with formal conference facilities at the Hong Kong Innovation Center, which resembled a teaching environment. Shifting from such a formal place to the open space (on the way) and finally into the unfamiliar interior of the nursing home had great impact on the students' experiences. It was a long journey from the workshop venue to the nursing home where Granny T lives. The students appeared relaxed as soon as they left the center. They clustered in small groups, excitedly chatting about irrelevant topics along the way. They enjoyed the 'break' so much that most of them even missed the subway train that Granny T had got on at the departure station. The entire group managed to meet at the designated station eventually. On the following bus journey, the students chose to sit beside their fellows, and the seat next to Granny T remained empty all the way. On entering the nursing home, the student designers seemed to quickly shift back to the 'working' mode, and started taking pictures everywhere, as if they were reminded of their task by the special facilities installed in the building and the particular spatial arrangement there. On the other hand, they were overwhelmed by this unfamiliar place. The playfulness continued somehow. The noisy and excited parade was so unusual to the elderly people who live there that some of them even sat at their bedroom doors, staring at the 'invaders' silently. Granny T had to introduce the students to her neighbors by emphasizing several times that they were her granddaughter's friends. She did not mention a word about the workshop event. The objective of this journey was meant to observe the ways Granny T managed her living at the nursing home. However, designers' own experiences of that place, physically and psychologically, were completely neglected in their group discussion, as if understanding user experience could be easily achieved by placing the user in question back to the user's own

living conditions and leaving designers themselves outside. The focus on the ‘other’ makes designers adopt an objective attitude, while self experience as an access to user experience is ignored. As Schutz [20] argued, understanding could be better achieved if the listeners grasp the meaning of a statement in its immediacy.

Furthermore, from a phenomenological perspective, Granny T’s bedroom and part of the public space in the nursing home are considered as an extension of her body. By allowing students into this place, she literally revealed her living there to the ‘others’, while the students did not realize the fact that the space around them is also part of Granny T. They kept chatting and making loud noises everywhere, even in the narrow corridors. They did not hesitate when they entered granny’s tiny bedroom, as one normally will do when getting into to a personal space bubble of the other. Students continuously missed the experiences disclosed by perceiving the space. Having finished their visit, they conducted a group discussion about design opportunity identification in the common room of the nursing home, leaving Granny T silently sitting in the same room alone. No one felt any inappropriateness since designers were working now. This small space where every member was present accentuates the literal alienation that was going on. So far, it had reached the peak of user-exclusion which is totally against the “the ethos of participatory design” [8]. It would have been a good opportunity to understand what being alienated from the co-creator identity means to a user-participant, since space staged and disclosed the embodied experience. However, the participants failed to tune into the embodied and imaginative dimension of Granny T’s experience of being isolated. Without probing into self experience as the context to approach the other’s, designers lose an important avenue to ‘act into’ the intersubjective process of empathy.

In 3.1 and 3.2 above, we attempt to explicate several natural attitudes in design that hinder empathy process to different extents. Firstly, we discussed how problem solving and a conceptualization tradition presented as a fixed role of designers hinders student designers from ‘connecting with’ the users/active-design-partners; secondly, we argued that, without knowing the ‘aesthesiological layer of the other’ [16] by allowing self experience disclosure, ‘acting into’ the intersubjective realm of experience becomes out of the question, which is illustrated with the example of spatial impacts on one’s bodily experience. The next section is on the process of merging with and on how designers deal with this process.

3.3. Practicing embodied empathy as a process

Empathy grounded on intersubjectivity helps us understand user experience. Namely, there is ultimately something in common in individual’s intending toward a thing in the world. This shared realm of experience can be achieved through reciprocally understanding self experience when experiencing the others’. Understanding self experience, however, is not easy, because it takes reflective effort to transcend from immediate experience and natural attitudes. Husserl suggested that individuals are expected to transpose themselves to the other’s place to achieve the meditation of empathy. Therefore, it is necessary for the researcher to experience how subjects experience their lives *in situ*. As Husserl suggested: ‘I secure [the person’s] motivations by placing myself in his situation, [with] his level of education, his development as a youth, etc., and to do so *I must needs share in that situation*; I not only empathize with his thinking, his feeling, and his action, but I must also *follow* him in them ... [14, 16].’ We maintain that these two phenomenological tasks, namely using the method of *epoche* and ‘a concretely dynamical spatializing of imaging’, should be fulfilled in our understanding of the user in design

research. Here we present how empathy was practiced in the Design.Live Workshop 2009.

In the workshop, the organizers Lee and Ho asked the students to listen to the details of the active-design-partners. This is the initial step of constituting intersubjectivity. As Finlay suggests, ‘the researcher’s task is not simply to listen to another’s story: the researcher also needs to be open to being with the participant in a relationship [14]. To avoid being trapped between the user as an empty concept with a collective identity and a user in person as active partner with unique experience and knowledge, it is necessary to encourage designers/researchers to construct detailed descriptions of the person. Mattelmaki, in his discussion of taking probing for co-exploring, pointed out that “we wanted especially to value the individual people’s experiences as the main drivers of the process. Persona descriptions ... were applied to disseminate the interpretations based on the probes and interviews. The objective with personas is to draw attention to potential users, support the creation of a common understanding of the users and to engage designers in implementing this understanding in their design decisions [13]. ” However, oftentimes persona is taken as a tool for constructing an empty concept with the collective identity of a user. Our personal description is a detailed record of one’s history and experiences, through which we attempt to understand such a personal account by making reference to the immediate situation. Following this initial activity, the designers/researcher should practice ‘doing empathy’ by connecting of the other’s embodiment to one’s own. Essentially, it is to achieve empathetic understanding of an other’s embodied experience by intimately connecting to the lived experience of the designer/researcher’s own. Our practice of empathy is based on both the personal account and the empathetic understanding.

Another group’s practice in the workshop showed the promising result of this probing activity. This group presented a cheerful game that every participant enjoyed, including their active-design-partner B. B is a young girl who cannot hear but is a lip-reader. Being close together with B, the students found that she is passionate for life and possesses a keen sense of color. Her stories struck a chord with the students since they have similar aspirations for fun as youngsters. Here B’s personal account provides the data for the designers to acquire the unique individuality of B. The following is drawn from the notes jotted down by the facilitator of this group:

“When comparing questions between what they had written down and those raised by B (the active-design-partner), the students discovered that they were able to give answers to a majority of the questions posed by themselves. They realized that they had asked stupid questions. They were reminded of starting from listening and talking (i.e., from mutual exchange), and the possibility of asking what B likes to do. In order to understand her more, they tried to discover what B’s strengths are and further to ask why she likes to do it. Finally the students found B’s interest in art, drawings, and photography, and understood that these activities could facilitate her expression of inner feelings. B loves photo-shooting, because colorful world to her is equivalent to music rhythm (as she could not hear music).” (Field note, B’s Group.)

The facilitator then made use of the personal description to consolidate the idea of the unique experience of B. The focus was not on the feelings and emotions throughout the growing up trajectory of B, but on her

embodiment. Student designers were encouraged to connect with B's bodily experiences.

“B is very sensitive to color. I asked the students if they know the reasons. I asked them to imagine one is staying below water, almost incapable of hearing anything, and see if they could find that images are much more prominent. So I asked them to cover their ears and walk for a distance in order to feel from the user's angle, to put one's feet into the user's shoes. Design thinking could start from our five senses to feel. We asked ourselves if we lost two senses, what would be the replacements? The students came to the conclusion that we could use lighting, visible and figurative hints and vibration as the substitutes. So, I asked the students to dig up more about B's strengths, try to ask more questions from the bright side, and do not continue to focus on the supposedly dark side of the active-design-partner.” (Field note, B's Group.)

Apart from connecting with the other's embodiment to one's own, the act of acting into the other's bodily experience brought forth the imagination of replacement. When the facilitator asked the students to cover their ears and walk for a distance, the second layer of empathy occurred. The most critical element in conceiving the 'final design' is the involvement of the active-design-partner and the students' imagination of being under the water. This is the experience the students were unfamiliar with. Probing into their embodied responses opened up rich understanding about the user. As Finlay [14] suggests, following Spiegelberg, “empathizing is not simply about putting oneself in the other's shoes. Instead, one has to leave behind one's own context and understandings to imaginatively project oneself into the Other's situation in an attempt to see the world through their eyes.” This approach not only allows students to understand the feelings of being in a soundless world, but also includes the active-design-partner into participation to enjoy the exploration of what kind of activity they all would enjoy. It appears to be able to fulfill one of the objectives of inclusive design as the facilitator pointed out: “students through the workshop are able to discern that the aim of design might not be a professionally designed product which would conversely provide an icon to 'label' the active-design-partner and to elevate their disabilities to the status of core identity. This is not a good design.”

Figure 1. The development of the game: 'Music without Sound'

Consequently, the outcome of the collective efforts emerged as a game, a kind of translation from music to action. At the final presentation, the group performed a silent piece of music. A 'conductor' translated the melody of a song into gestures that were supposed to be signals conveyed to the 'musicians'. Musicians (including B) lined up, and each held two transparent bottles filled with water in various vivid colors. Under the direction of the conductor, they shook the colorful bottles in different bodily movement with a unique rhythm. Upon finishing the game, the group eagerly asked the audience whether they could feel it *was* actually a music piece the way

they did. Apparently, design partner B's unique experience had been translated through a synaesthesia attempt, which was achieved, empathetically, through student designers' entering B's experience of music aided by imagination with colors and rhythms. This echoes Finlay's suggestion of the third layer of empathy, i.e., merging with the other's bodily experience. This example illustrates the importance of empathy which starts from personal descriptions, and is practiced throughout the three interrelated intersubjective layers as a process.

4. Concluding remarks

While understanding user experience has been posited at the core of the array of design practices varying from user-centered design to participatory design or co-design, the conventional designers-and-users framework cannot be easily suspended, which controversially hinders understanding of the users and the co-creation process. Based on our experiences from the Design.Live Workshop 2009, we adopt the phenomenological perspective to analyze the layers of embodied relationship, namely empathy, between 'users' and novice designers, and to what extent they are interrupted by designers' natural attitudes. We argue that practicing empathy as a process by suspending designers' natural attitudes could facilitate the change of attitude toward seeing users-as-active-partners or users-as-co-creators as well as better inclusion of 'users' in design.

It is worthy of notice though, natural attitudes are the taken for granted perspectives, where designers exercise their expertise to fulfill varied design tasks, contain knowledge and experience that are crucial to not only designers but also design as a discipline. The attempt to suspend them is different from the attempt to eliminate them. Being aware of the potential impacts of designers' natural attitudes on practicing interrelated layers of empathy as a process provides more opportunities to understand user experience. It offers a different perspective to disclose the real needs and experiences and lays down a potential foundation to address the form, the extent and the nature of co-creation.

Furthermore, concerning the ethos of participatory design, the responsibility of inclusive designers as social activists is not to reinforce design partners' problematic situations through sympathy. It is true that the 'disabled' people invited as design partners into inclusive design have their problems. However, the co-creator identity of users as active-design-partners should be earned through the effort of everyone involved to "push the focus from the needs and rights of disabled people and more to real inclusion of individual lifestyles rather than integration. [6]" The challenge of inclusive design is to be inspired from a unique perspective, using empathy to better understand user experience, to engage all participants to contribute to design as an activity where they feel empowered to do so and really appreciate the way they design as well as what they design. A user as an active partner is a new design attitude for the students, which cannot be internalized by practicing without continuous reflections on it and learning to tune themselves to discourse with a new colleague. Even more general design practices may thus benefit. In this article, we suggest that, in design research and hopefully in design education, phenomenological analysis and skills in empathy should be incorporated to find out feasible ways for the formation of mutual understanding and intersubjectivity.

5. References

[1] Simon, H. (1996). *The Sciences of Artificial*. (3rd ed). London: The MIT Press.

- [2] Dorst, K. (2008). Design research: a revolution-waiting-to-happen, *Design Studies*, 29(1), 4-11.
- [3] Sanders, E.B.-N., & Stappers, P. J. (2008). Co-creation and the new landscapes of design, *CoDesign*, 4(1), 5-18.
- [4] Lee, Y. (2008). Design participation tactics: the challenges and new roles for designers in the co-design process, *CoDesign*, 4(1), 31-50.
- [5] Cassim, J. (2007). 'It's Not what you do it's the way that you do it: the Challenge Workshop a designer-centered inclusive design knowledge transfer mechanism for different contexts,' *Human Computer Interaction International (HCI)*, July 2007, Beijing, China.
- [6] Lee, Y., Cassim, J. (2009). How the Inclusive Design Process Enables Social Inclusion, *proceedings of IASDR 2009 Conference*, (pp.1-10).
- [7] Binder, T., Brandt, E., & Gregory, J. (2008) Editorial: Design participation(-s), *CoDesign*, 4(1), 1-3.
- [8] Brereton, M., & Buur, J. (2008). New Challenges for design participation in the era of ubiquitous computing, *CoDesign*, 4(2), 101-113.
- [9] Fischer, G. (2002). Beyond 'couch potatoes': from consumers to designers and active contributors. *First Monday*, 7(12). Available online at: <http://firstmonday.org/htbin/cgiwrap/bin/ojs/index.php/fm/article/view/1010/931>. [Accessed 15 Mar, 2010]
- [10] Brodersen, C., Dindler, C., & Iversen, O. S. (2008). Staging imaginative places for participatory prototyping, *CoDesign*, 4(1), 19-30.
- [11] de Certeau, M. (1984). *The practice of everyday life*. Berkely, CA: University of California Press.
- [12] Björgvinsson, E. B. (2008). Open-ended participatory design as prototypical practice, *CoDesign*, 4(2), 85-99.
- [13] Mattelmäki, T. (2008). Probing for co-exploring, *CoDesign*, 4(1), 65-78.
- [14] Finlay, L. (2005). "Reflexive Embodied Empathy": A Phenomenology of Participant-Researcher Intersubjectivity, *The Humanistic Psychologist*, 33(4), 271-292.
- [15] Stein, E. (1989). *On the problem of empathy* (3rd ed.; W. Stein, trans.). Washington, D.C.: ICS Publications. (Original work published 1916)
- [16] Husserl, E. (1989). *Ideas pertaining to a pure phenomenology and to a phenomenological philosophy, second book: Studies in the phenomenology of constitution* (R. Rojcewicz & A. Schuwer, Trans.) Boston: Kluwer. (Original work written in 1928 and published posthumously in 1952)
- [17] Sokolowski, B. (2000). *Introduction to Phenomenology*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- [18] Verbeek, P.-P., & KockelKoren, P. (1998). The Things That Matter, *Design Issues*, 14(3), 28-42.
- [19] Merleau-Ponty, M. (1962). *Phenomenology of perception* (C. Smith, Trans.). London: Routledge & Kegan Paul. (Original work published 1945)
- [20] Schutz, A. (1964). *Collected Papers 2: Studies in Social Theory*. The Hague: Martinus Nijhoff.